

**Designing a Roadmap for
Effective and Sustainable Strategies for
Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of
EU Agriculture to Navigate within a
Safe and Just Operating Space**

**Policy-Driven Shifts in Crop
Choices – A Case Study on the
German Implementation of the
EU Nitrates Directive**

Discussion paper

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Policy-Driven Shifts in Crop Choices – A Case Study on the German Implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive

Abstract

Context: Farmers' crop choices are shaped by economic factors, natural conditions, and policy interventions. While some policies directly target cropping decisions, others can unintentionally influence farmers' crop choices. Understanding these indirect effects is essential for preventing unintended environmental consequences and accurately assessing the economic implications. In Germany, the revised implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive introduced extensive management restrictions in areas with high nitrate pollution, such as additional restrictions on manure application and overall fertilizer use. However, its impact on farm-level decision-making, particularly cropping decisions, remains largely unexplored.

Objective: This study investigates whether the revised implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive in Germany leads to short-term adjustments in crop choices, shedding light on how regulatory changes shape agricultural land use.

Methods: We apply a differences-in-differences approach with staggered treatment timing to account for changes in the definition of nitrate-polluted areas. Estimations are performed within a Probabilistic Programming framework, providing a Bayesian representation of uncertainty. As a case study, we analyze the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, where up to 30% of agricultural land is designated as nitrate-polluted.

Results and Conclusion: Our findings indicate that the short-term effects of nitrate-polluted area designations on crop choices are modest, with all observed changes being smaller than 2% points. Overall, the policy has a reducing effect on the cultivation of maize and winter cereals other than winter wheat while an increasing effect on winter wheat, sugar beet, and rapeseed. However, these effects vary over time, suggesting that farmers adjust their adoption behavior as the policy remains in place longer and larger areas are classified as nitrate-polluted. From a policy perspective, we conclude that measures might be less limiting than suggested by the public debate and that missing knowledge might hinder the optimal adaptation of crop choices.

Keywords: EU Nitrates Directive, Crop Choice, Fertilizer Regulation, Bayesian Inference, Probabilistic Programming

1 Introduction

Farmers' crop choices are determined by complex interactions between market signals, personal preferences, and agronomic restrictions. The resulting crop sequences and their diversity are linked to various dimensions of the Safe and Just Space Operating space (Müller et al., 2024), and particularly impact biodiversity outcomes (e.g., Strobl 2022), novel entities (e.g., Guinet et al., 2023) and food security (e.g., Renard and Tilman 2019). Current, EU agri-environmental policies compensate for diverse crop sequences or specific crops with a high agronomic or environmental benefit. However, policies targeting goals other than crop diversity can also impact farmers' crop choices. In Germany, for instance, the support of biogas plants as part of the Renewable Energy Act has led to more silage maize production as feedstock (Lüker-Jans et al., 2017), and a regional simplification of crop sequences (Csikos et al., 2019). In contrast, the increase in organic production supported by funding schemes goes along with more diverse crop sequences than conventional counterparts (see Reumaux et al. 2023 for an example from Sweden). These side effects of policies on crop choices must be detected and integrated into their ex-post and ex-ante evaluation to avoid unintended negative environmental, economic, and social implications.

In Germany, the Fertilizer Application Ordinance (FO) implements the EU Nitrates Directive and is the central agri-environmental policy to limit the loss of nitrogen (N) from farming systems. It underwent fundamental changes over the last years in response to the EU Commission's treaty violation proceedings against Germany. At the core of the last revision in 2020 are stricter measures in nitrate-polluted areas (polluted areas in the following) where high nitrate concentrations in groundwater bodies are found. The stricter measures cover, amongst others, lower fertilization thresholds based on compulsory fertilization planning, plot instead of farm-specific restriction on manure application, stricter banning of fertilizer application in autumn, and compulsory catch crop cultivation before spring crops. There was a public and scientific debate on the consequences for agricultural production (Kage et al., 2022; Taube, 2023). Advisory services and agricultural press propagate the adaptation of crop choices in response to the policy, focusing on introducing spring crops such as maize and sugar beet whose N need aligns well with soil N mineralization and that have relatively high N needs accounted in the fertilization plans. However, empirical evidence to what extent farmers followed this advice is lacking. Hence, this paper addresses the question of whether the revised implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive led to short-term changes in crop choices in polluted areas.

The impact of the EU Nitrates Directives on crop choices has not been researched yet. We partly fill this gap by contributing the first empirical analysis of the short-term adaptation

of crop choices, focusing on polluted areas of the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW). The policy strongly affects this state, as 33% of the agricultural land falls into polluted areas (LANUV, 2024), and agricultural production is, in part, highly intensive with large regional nutrient surpluses (NRW, 2021). Capturing the crop choices allows insights into the possible side effects of the policy on crop diversity and further unintended consequences and possible implications of the policy, including the compliance costs. Methodically, we apply an Bayesian Probabilistic Programming (PP) approach allowing to derive Bayesian posterior distributions for the estimated quantities (Storm et al., 2024). Finally, our study aims to provide a blueprint for analyzing other spatial differentiated policies and their implication on crop choices, such as management restrictions in Natura 2000 or water protection areas. As such policies are in place in all EU countries and beyond, the research is of interest for a broad scientific policy.

The paper is structured as follows. In the next section, we provide an overview of the used data, the FO, and the definition of the polluted areas. Furthermore, we describe the applied empirical estimation approach. Then, we present the results before we discuss their implications. We conclude in the last section.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Case study region and data

We focus our analysis on the German Federal state of NRW, characterized by a high share of polluted areas and intensive agricultural production. Between 2020 and 2022, around 11% of the agricultural area was designated as a polluted area (NRW, 2021, 2023), as shown in Figure 1. The share increased to 33% under the General Administrative Regulation 2022 (LANUV, 2024). The state has concentrated pig and poultry production in the northern part and high numbers of biogas plants. Dairy production is located in the low mountain ranges in the southern part and the Lower Rhine, with high shares of grassland (NRW, 2021). Arable farming production is dominated by maize at 28%, winter wheat at 23%, winter barley at 13%, and winter rape seed at 5%. Sugar beet and potatoes have a share of 5% and 4%, respectively (in 2022, own calculation based on NRW 2025), and are mainly found on the high-yielding soils in the western part (LWK NRW, 2021). We use data from the EU Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) that the German federal states collect to settle Common Agricultural Policy interventions, such as direct payments under the first pillar. The Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) is part of the IACS and contains all agricultural land parcels based on ortho imagery that predefines the agricultural area eligible for interventions. The data used in this study contains the spatially explicit plot geometries and crop use for 2019 to 2024 that farmers

provide in their application for direct payments. The data is publicly available (NRW, 2025), which facilitates the replication of the study. We use the geometries of the plots from 2024 and match them to the geometries from 2019 to 2023 with the largest overlap. While this approach might lead to slight inaccuracies it enables the analysis of plot-specific crop sequences. We use data from the official administrative bodies on the polluted areas. The data provide the shape of the designated area and a categorization of plots from the IACS data that fall within the area (see Figure 1).

(a) Polluted areas according to $red_{r=1}$

(b) Polluted areas according to $red_{r=2}$

(c) Polluted areas according to $red_{r=3}$

Figure 1: Definition of polluted area across the three relevant regulations, where $red_1 = \text{Landesdüngerverordnung 2019:2}$, $red_2 = \text{Landesdüngerverordnung 2019:3}$, and $red_3 = \text{Landesdüngerverordnung 2022:1, 2022:2, 2022:03}$.

2.2 Measures and definition of polluted areas

Additional measures in polluted areas were introduced first with the FO 2017 (Table 1); however, they were relatively weak. The FO 2020 contains numerous additional, far-reaching measures for the polluted areas. Most prominently, the N target value of crops, which farmers have to calculate following a predefined protocol and meet with their fertilizing activities, is lowered by 20% on average for all fields of a farm within polluted areas. This results in a lower allowed N fertilization; however, the reduction has not to be realized equally on all fields but needs to be met on average for the fields within the polluted areas.

Furthermore, the application limit for manure N of 170 kg ha⁻¹a⁻¹ has to be met at the plot instead of the farm level, reducing the flexibility to shift organic fertilization to crops such as maize. There are exceptions for the reduced N target value and plot-specific manure accounting for farms with low N input.

Several additional measures restrict the time and amount of fertilizer applied in autumn and winter, considering that the risk of leaching losses is highest in these seasons. Banning periods for fertilizer application start on grassland on October 1st instead of November 1st. For solid manure, the FO extends the banning period in polluted areas, lasting from November 1st to January 31st instead of December 1st to January 15th. In autumn and after the harvest of the main crop, fertilizer application of a maximum of 60 kg N ha⁻¹a⁻¹ is generally allowed outside of polluted areas to catch crops, rape seed, field forage, winter barley after cereals, and certain berries and vegetables. In polluted areas, however, it is only allowed to apply fertilizer to rape seed after soil testing, field forage, catch crops for feed use, and, all catch crops in the form of solid manure. Manure application is additionally restricted in polluted areas on grassland and multi-annual field forage. Between September 1st and the start of the fixed banning periods, the FO allows the application of 60 kg N ha⁻¹a⁻¹ in polluted areas instead of 80 kg N ha⁻¹a⁻¹.

In addition, fertilizer can only be applied to summer crops if a catch crop has been established in the autumn before, except for arid areas and a late harvest of the previous crop after October 1st. This generally results in compulsory catch crop cultivation before most summer crops.

The stricter measures under the FO 2020 became compulsory on January 1, 2021, being relevant for the first time for the polluted areas defined under the FOS 2019:3 (1.01.2021 until 30.01.2022) and summer crops sown in summer 2021 (Table 1). Also, with the updated definition of polluted areas in the FOS 2022:1 (1.12.2022 until 5.7.2021), many additional areas were declared polluted where stricter measures were relevant for the first time for summer crops in 2023. For these cases, a right of continuance exists as farmers have already taken relevant management decisions before the new policy was in place or the field was declared polluted, as described by NRW (2023). First, summer crops

can be fertilized, although no catch crop has been cultivated in the winter. Second, the fertilizer threshold is not lowered when the fertilizer plans have already been made and fertilizer has already been applied. Third, the plot-specific manure application limit does not apply when manure has already been applied. This results in a stepwise introduction of the measures, and whether they apply or not can depend on management decisions not reflected in the data, making it difficult to estimate precisely when the treatment took place the first time. However, we account for the winter crops 2020/21 as the first treatment under the polluted area definition of the FOS (31.03.2020 until 31.12.2020). Although farmers did not yet have to follow the rules, some might have adapted to the policy before the actual enforcement.

We summarize which FOs is relevant for the different crop choice decisions in Table 2. The table distinguishes between summer and winter crops taking into account when farmers need to take the cropping decision and when FO regulations are published and binding.

2.3 Analysis set-up

The aim of the paper is to estimate how stricter fertilization regulations applying to some fields impact farmers' crop-choice decisions. The identification strategy builds on a Difference-in-Difference (DiD) approach. The treatment in our context is tighter fertilization regulations within the polluted areas (also called "red areas"). Intuitively, we compare how crop shares within polluted areas develop before and after treatment while correcting for the change in crop shares in non-treated areas. As we discuss in the following, we need to deal with the challenge that we have a staggered treatment that can turn on and off (i.e., treatment is not an absorbing state and can be reversed). Additionally, we consider different options to relax the parallel trends assumption underlying the DiD identification strategy (see Roth et al. 2023 for a recent review of DiD methods). For estimation, we employ a Bayesian estimation approach to obtain full Bayesian posterior distributions for the estimated parameters.

As outlined in section 2.2 there are three different regulations that farmers need to comply with over time. Depending on when the regulation was "active" and considering when farmers make cropping decisions for summer and winter crops, we have a treatment pattern as given in table 2. Additionally, the analysis needs to consider that the assignment of fields as polluted areas varies across the three relevant regulations. As can be seen visually in the maps in figure 1, the definition of red areas changes quite substantially across the three regulations. For the three different regulations, there are 8 different combinations of possible treatment patterns. Table 3 shows the frequency of these eight options.

<p>Measures related to the polluted areas from the Fertilizer Application Ordinance (“Düngerordnung”) at the state level</p>	<p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance 2017.</p> <p>Prescribes that nitrate-polluted areas are defined in line with the German Groundwater Ordinance (“Grundwasserverordnung”).</p> <p>The federal government must select at least three additional measures in nitrate-polluted areas from a predefined list.</p> <p>Came into force on 1.06.2017.</p>	<p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance 2020</p> <p>It prescribes that nitrate-polluted areas are defined following the Groundwater Ordinance and how pollution within groundwater bodies can be differentiated, referencing the General Administrative Regulation.</p> <p>The following measures are compulsory within nitrate-polluted areas. - N fertilization 20% below target value derived from the fertilizing planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organic N limit of 170 kg ha-1 on the plot instead of farm level - longer banning periods for fertilization - on arable land, no fertilization in autumn except for rape seed after soil testing and solid manure for catch crops - on grassland, stronger limitation of fertilization in autumn - catch crops after summer crops compulsory except when no fertilizer is applied the next year, harvest after 1.10 and arid areas <p>The federal state governments must select at least two additional measures in nitrate-polluted areas.</p> <p>It came into force on 1.05.2020, and regulations on polluted areas became compulsory on 1.01.2021.</p>
<p>General Administrative Regulation concretizes and harmonizes the proceedings of federal states in defining nitrate-polluted areas (“Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift Gebietsausweisung”)</p>		<p>General Administrative Regulation 2020 (12.08.2020 - 14.6.2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prescribes method to differentiate nitrate pollution within groundwater bodies based on, amongst other, hydrogeologic and hydraulic boundaries as well as modeling results. <p>General Administrative Regulation 2022 (from 15.6.2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changes method of differentiation of nitrate pollution within groundwater bodies, excluding, amongst other, modeling results and including denitrification potential.
<p>The Fertilizer Application Ordinance of North Rhine-Westfalen defines the nitrate-polluted areas at the federal-state level and prescribes additional measures (“Landesdüngerordnung Nordrhein-Westfalen”)</p>	<p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance at the federal state level 2019:1 (1.3.2019 - 30.03.2020)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - defines polluted areas according to the management plan 2016-2021 under the Water Framework Directive - defines three additional measures in polluted areas: 1. compulsory nutrient testing of manure (from 1.8.2019), 2. incorporation of manure on bare soil within one hour, 3. stricter banning periods for manure application autumn on grassland 	<p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance at the federal state level 2019:2 (31.03.2020 - 31.12.2020)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - differentiation of polluted areas depending on additional monitoring and modeling (“Binnendifferenzierung NRW”) - additional measures identical to Ordinance 2019:1 <p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance at the federal state level 2019:3 (01.01.2021 - 30.11.2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - defines polluted areas in line with the General Administrative Regulation from 2020 - defines two additional measures in polluted areas: 1. compulsory nutrient testing of manure, 2. compulsory training on fertilization <p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance at the federal state level 2022:1 (1.12.2022 - 5.07.2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - defines polluted areas in line with General Administrative Regulation from 2022 - additional measures identical <p>Fertilizer Application Ordinance at the federal state level 2022:2 (6.07.2023 - 18.12.2023) and 2022:3 (from 19.12.2023)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - primarily updated for changing field geometries

Notes: N - nitrogen, NRW - North Rhine-Westphalia.

Table 1: Measures of Fertilizer Application Ordinance concerning the nitrate-polluted areas and complementary regulations in the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia,

Winter crop	19	20	21	22	23	24
$red_{r=1}$	o	o	x	o	o	o
$red_{r=2}$	o	o	o	x	x	o
$red_{r=3}$	o	o	o	o	o	x
Summer crop	19	20	21	22	23	24
$red_{r=1}$	o	o	o	o	o	o
$red_{r=2}$	o	o	x	x	o	o
$red_{r=3}$	o	o	o	o	x	x

Table 2: Treatment assignment, \mathbf{treat}_t , for winter and summer crops. Here "x" indicates that the policy is relevant, i.e. treatment is active, for the respective crop choice decision, while "o" indicates that it is not relevant (see Figure 1 for the definition of $red_r : r = 1, 2, 3$)

To model field-level cropping decisions we use a reduced-form model specification. Specifically, we assume that the decision to grow a specific crop, $crop_{i,t} = \{0, 1\}$, on field i in year t is a Bernoulli distribution governed by a probability $P(crop_{i,t})$:

$$crop_{i,t} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(P(crop_{i,t})) \quad (1)$$

We assume that the probability of a crop, $P(crop_{i,t})$, is determined by

$$P(crop_{i,t}) = f(\mathbf{m}_i, \mathbf{w}_i, \mathbf{red}_i, \mathbf{treat}_t) \quad (2)$$

with $f(\cdot)$ being a link function that maps inputs to a probability. This specification allows that $P(crop_{i,t})$ depends on individual field characteristics \mathbf{m}_i and regional characteristics \mathbf{w}_i . Additionally, it allows that crop probabilities differ between fields assigned to the three different polluted area definitions $\mathbf{red}_i \equiv (red_{ri} : r = 1, 2, 3)$ and on wheater these regulations are binding $\mathbf{treat}_t \equiv (treat_{rt} : r = 1, 2, 3)$ in the respective year. Here, red_{ri} is a binary variable specifying if field i is a polluted area according to FO $r = 1, 2, 3$ and $treat_{rt}$ is a binary variable if FO r is binding in year t (see table 2).

We start with a simple model specification and extend it stepwise. In this specification, we assume that there is a different base probability $\omega_{\tilde{r}} \equiv (\omega_{\tilde{r}} = 0, 1)$ between polluted $\tilde{r} = 1$ and non-polluted areas $\tilde{r} = 0$ (note that we do not distinguish between the three different FO $r = 1, 2, 3$, but instead consider only a binary differentiation here). We use an index variable notation, where $\tilde{r}[i]$ denotes if field i is either polluted $\tilde{r} = 1$ or non-polluted $\tilde{r} = 0$. Further, we assume that there are year-fixed effects (τ_t) and that treatment effects, θ_t , of the FO regulation vary by year.

$$P(crop_{i,t}) = f(\omega_{Red[i]}, \tau_t, \theta_t) \quad (3)$$

For the link function $f(\cdot)$ we consider a logistic function $f(x) = \text{logit}^{-1}(x) = (1 + e^{-x})^{-1}$

$red_{r=1}$	$red_{r=2}$	$red_{r=3}$	Count
0	0	0	173.308
0	0	1	52.979
0	1	0	49
0	1	1	13.131
1	0	0	23.890
1	0	1	28.483
1	1	0	1.533
1	1	1	34.494
Total			327.867

Table 3: Number of fields in each of the 8 treatment combination that are possible from the three different polluted area regulations (see Figure 1 for the definition of $red_r : r = 1, 2, 3$)

leading to:

$$P(crop_{i,t}) = \text{logit}^{-1}(L_{i,t}) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\omega_{\tilde{r}[i]} + \tau_t + \theta_t \text{Treat}_{\tilde{r}[i],t}) \quad (4)$$

This specification is similar to what Roth et al. (2023) calls the canonical Difference-in-Difference (DiD) setup with the extension that we need to deal with a staggered adoption patten. Identification in this model relies on a set of assumptions. 1) We need to assume that there are no spillovers between treated and control units, i.e. that fields outside polluted areas are not affected by the treatment of polluted areas. This assumption could be violated if farmers move crops out of polluted areas into neighboring polluted areas. However, those effects are only likely to occur at the border between polluted and non-polluted areas, and as we consider all fields in NRW that are none-polluted as the control group, this potential effect is expected to be limited. 2) We need to assume that farms do not anticipate treatment and adjust crop choices before the treatment regulation becomes binding. We aim to control for this as best as possible as discussed in section 2.2 by defining treatment assingment accordingly. 3) Further, a crucial assumption of the DiD identification strategy is the *parallel trends* assumptions. In the specific case of a staggered adoption case identification rest on the assumption that the (unobserved) none-treatment development for all possible treatment groups would have been the same as for the none-treated groups (see Roth et al. 2023, assumption 4)¹. This is a quite strong assumption as polluted areas might be structurally different with potentially different trends. One option to relax the parallel trend assumption is to assume parallel trends only after conditioning on field or regional characteristics (see Roth et al. 2023, section 4

¹. Note that technically, given the model specification, we need to assume parallel trends in *logits*, $L_{i,t}$, not in probability itself.

for a review of existing approaches). We implement this specification by extending 4 to :

$$P(crop_{i,t}) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\omega_{\bar{r}[i]} + \tau_t + \mathbf{m}_i\gamma_t^m + \mathbf{w}_i\gamma_t^w + \theta_t\text{Treat}_{\bar{r}[i],t}) \quad (5)$$

As regional control variables, \mathbf{w}_i , we consider the density of cattle, the density of pigs, as well as the density of biogas plants per region. For the field-level control variables \mathbf{m}_i we include the log field size (in ha) and a soil quality rating (*Bodenzahl*). Intuitively, in terms of the parallel trend assumption, the specification assumes that treated observations would have developed similarly under non-treatment as the non-treated units when comparing treated and non-treated units that are the same in terms of their regional and field characteristics. As such, this specification allows us to account for structural differences. Estimation of equation (5) is performed using *NumPyro* (Bingham et al., 2019; Phan et al., 2019), a Bayesian Probabilistic Programming framework. To implement the outline model, we need to make further assumptions specifying the prior distributions for the unknown parameters. We choose weakly informative priors given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{\bar{r}} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.5) \\ \tau_t &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.5) \\ \gamma_t^m &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.1) \\ \gamma_t^w &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.1) \\ \theta_t &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.5) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equation (1), (5), and (6) specify a complete data-generating-process (DAG). These equations are implemented in *NumPyro* allowing to condition the model on observed quantities $crop_{i,t}$, \mathbf{m}_i , \mathbf{w}_i , \mathbf{red}_i , and \mathbf{treat}_t to derive conditional posterior distributions for the unknown parameters. Inference is performed using NumPyro’s *No U-Turn Sampler* (NUTS) Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampler. Estimation is based on crop choice information from 327.867 fields (see table 3) observed yearly for the years (2019-2024), resulting in almost 2 million observations available for estimation. We exclude very small fields, i.e., those smaller than 0.5ha. We estimate the model for six different crop groups, comprising the most relevant crops in grown in the region.

3 Results

The estimated posterior effects of the model, defined by equation (1), (5), and (6), are presented in Figure 2. The figure shows the estimated DiD treatment effects for the six different crop groups considered. The solid lines indicate the median posterior effects, while the shaded areas show the 94% highest posterior density intervals (HDI), reflecting

the posterior uncertainty in the estimated effects. An estimated treatment effect of 1% point implies that, given the data and the model assumptions, the probability of a crop within polluted areas is 1%point higher than if it had not been treat, i.e., assigned as an polluted area. The overall effects are rather modest, in all cases the effects in absolute terms are smaller than 2% points (even when taking into account parameter uncertainty, i.e., the shaded areas). It also becomes apparent that estimated effects are quite heterogeneous across crops and time periods.

Figure 2: Estimated treatment effects for six different crop groups. Solid lines indicate the estimated median posterior effects. Shaded areas provide the 94% highest posterior density intervals (HDI).

4 Discussion

Our analysis estimates the crop choice changes induced by the stricter measures in polluted areas. We judge the overall effects as small, especially in relation to the discussion on the measures before their implementation. Furthermore, we do not find an increase in spring-sown crops such as maize and spring cereals as propagated by extension services in response to the 20% reduction in the N fertilizer thresholds. Several reasons could cause this. First, due to the novelty of the policy, farmers might not be aware of optimal adaptation measures. Second, compulsory fertilizer planning accounts for a relatively high N need that does not restrict farmers in their fertilizing activities and, hence, does not cause adaption of crop choices. This reason is linked to the third point, which is

that the yield reduction induced by the fertilizer reduction might be relatively small and is more cost-efficient to cope with small yield reductions than adapt the crop choice. However, long-term yield reduction might be larger when the N pool in the soil and the N mineralization is lower, especially as the use of organic N is also restricted in polluted areas.

In contrast, the policy measures have a decreasing effect on the probability of maize. We hypothesize that the plot-specific manure application restrictions and the compulsory catch crop cultivation are potential drivers. Farmers tend to apply more manure in maize than 170 kg N and fertilize other crops primarily with mineral N fertilizer. Compulsory catch crop cultivation before maize may cause additional costs and might be challenging when the pre-crop is harvested late.

Our results show a large temporal heterogeneity, with partly contrasting effects, even when taking the estimated uncertainty into account. There are several explanations for this. First, the extent of polluted areas increased in the research period, meaning that there are more farms with no or little non-polluted areas. If farmers react to the regulation by moving certain crops out of polluted areas but do not adapt their overall crop shares, the increase of polluted areas reduces flexibility for farms and might cause contrasting effects on crops. Second, the ability to adapt might be larger short than long term. Farmers remove certain crops, such as maize, from rotations on land in polluted areas, and after some years, they are included again to realize rotational breaks between crops. Third, farmers might overreact to the regulations and have experienced over the years that cultivating crops such as maize is not an issue under management restrictions in polluted areas.

The results of the study might differ for a long-term evaluation. The analysis covers four years and, hence, eight cropping decisions since the implementation of stricter measures in polluted areas and, therefore, covers a relatively new policy. On the one hand, the designation of polluted areas changed several times during the study period, causing insecurities for farmers, and they might not have found their optimal adaptation strategy. Furthermore, knowledge of crop adoption to reduce compliance costs with the FO might not be widely spread. This may result in a larger adaptation of crop choices in the long term. On the other hand, the flexibility of crop sequence adjustments might be larger in the short run than in the long run, as farms may need to return to wider rotation after several years.

From a policy perspective, the small changes in crop shares and the decreasing effect on maize raise several questions. First, measures might be of little limitation for farmers as no adoption is needed. However, our findings do not inform about other management changes and induced yield reduction. Second, maize is an advantageous crop concerning the total fertilizer limitation, but as a spring-sown crop usually fertilized with high amounts of

manure, it is more affected by the compulsory catch crop cultivation and the plot-specific restriction of 170 kg N ha⁻¹a⁻¹. These latter measures have received little attention in public debate. Our results suggest that such regulations influence crop choices and should be considered in ongoing discussions about exemptions for environmentally friendly farmers in polluted areas. Finally, total fertilizer limitations appear to be less relevant for farmers' crop choice decisions than anticipated, this might be relevant to consider for further policy adjustment aiming to achieve environmental goals.

5 Conclusion

This study examines whether the revised implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive in Germany induces short-term adjustments in crop choices. The revision comprises stricter regulations in designated nitrate-polluted areas, including additional restrictions on manure application and total fertilizer use. Using the German federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, where up to 30% of agricultural land is classified as nitrate-polluted, as a case study, our findings reveal that the overall effects on crop choices are small but highly heterogeneous across crops and over time. Overall, there is a decreasing effect of the policy on the cultivation of maize and winter cereals other than wheat and an increasing effect on sugar beet, rape seed, and winter wheat. From a policy perspective, several insights emerge from the modest observed changes in crop choices. We conclude, particularly regarding restrictions on overall fertilizer use, that there may be additional scope for further limitations if necessary to achieve environmental objectives. In addition, policymakers should assess whether adequate information and advisory services are sufficient to support farmers in adapting to the policy and enhance them if needed. Our findings on maize cultivation indicate that restrictions on manure application and catch crop cultivation might serve as a stronger incentive for adaptation than limits on total fertilizer use. This should be considered in ongoing discussions on potential exemptions for environmentally friendly farms in nitrate-polluted areas. However, as the policy has been in place for only a short period and our analysis is based on a relatively simple model specification, these conclusions should be regarded as preliminary and motivate further research.

In order to capture long-term effects it might be useful to repeat the analysis at a later stage. In this case, the evaluation can be done at the crop sequence instead of the crop level, which is enabled by the applied methodology. This allows for identifying side effects on crop diversity with a stronger link to environmental impacts. The provided workflow is a blueprint for analyzing any spatial differentiated policy and the induced changes in crop choice, which is, for example, relevant for Natura 2000 areas and water protection areas. The empirical findings from this study could be usefully complemented by follow-up

studies, using, for example, qualitative approaches on a sample of farms to detect farmers' motivation for adapting to the policy. Our research provides the empirical foundation for such work.

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